

Name	Mackenzie, Benjamin
Student Number	179073526/1
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Unit Convenor	Dr Sheila Samsatli (smcas20)
Personal Tutor	Dr Emma Emanuelsson Patterson (eaep20)

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IS RAINWATER HARVESTING A FEASIBLE WATER SUPPLY FOR FILTON AIRFIELD, BRISTOL

CE30122 – MENG Research Project

Written by Benjamin Mackenzie
Supervised by Jan Hofman, Amy Kim

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Name: Benjamin Mackenzie

Signature: *B. Mackenzie*

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Abstract

Water is a vital resource for human life, through direct consumption and indirect use in nearly all industries. Whilst conventional water supplies such as groundwater and surface water have been reliable in the past, this may change in the close future. Climate change, population growth and urbanisation are expected to increase the water stress of many regions. With current trajectories, many water supplies will not be able to sustainably handle future water demand. Furthermore, extreme rainfall patterns are expected to increase with climate change. Coupled with urbanisation, the risk of flash floods in populated areas is greatly increased. Rainwater harvesting (RWH) allows for an alternative source of water, which can reduce the pressure on existing water supplies and stormwater management systems.

The purpose of this report was to investigate the feasibility of rainwater harvesting as an additional water supply at a new development site in Filton, Bristol. **This site used a large hangar roof to collect rainwater for 278 houses.** To investigate this, Python software was used to create two models. The first was a stochastic model that would simulate rainfall, using probability distributions developed from historical rainfall data. The second was a behavioural model of the RWH tank. Using the simulated rainfall data as an input to the model, and demand simulated from KWR's SIMDEUM package as an output, this model calculated important variables for analysis. These variables were then used to calculate **water saving efficiency (WS), stormwater capture efficiency (SC) and reliability.**

The limitations of the stochastic model proved to be too inaccurate compared to using raw historical rainfall data. To improve **the viability of the RWH system, tank volume and set-point were to be optimised.** The optimum tank volume using historical data fell in the range of 70.7 m³ and 170.7 m³. To optimise this further before serious analysis, the tank costs and financial yield savings were considered. **The final chosen volume was 100 m³, providing a WS efficiency of 38.1%, SC efficiency of 87.5% and reliability of 28% when used to meet non-potable water demand of toilets and washing machines.** The objective of analysing the maximum set-point and rainfall threshold for this set-point could not be achieved due to a data restriction policy imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. Likewise, data could not be obtained for the operating and capital costs required for economic analysis.

It was concluded that RWH is likely to be a feasible supply, especially if the effect on stormwater reduction is considered. Although concrete evidence could not be obtained, similar literature appeared to come to the same conclusions. Future work analysing the stormwater reduction is recommended, as well as an investigation into a semi-centralised model.

1 Introduction

Water is arguably the most important resource for human life. Its high versatility provides use in many essential biological functions, including as a reactant or as a medium for other processes to occur (Chaplin, 2006). Most industries will use steam or liquid water in production whilst the waste, along with residential and other municipal sewage, will be transported for treatment using water. The biggest proportion of global water consumption can be found in agriculture, with 90% used for the irrigation of crops (Nazemi et al, 2014). Without water, human life is not viable.

To meet such a large demand, a variety of water sources are utilised. Whilst approximately 1386 million km³ of water is estimated to exist in the hydrosphere, fresh water comprises only 2.5% (Shiklomanov, 2000). Furthermore, 68.7% of this freshwater cannot be efficiently used as a source as it consists of ice found in glaciers or permanent snow cover. Therefore, the remaining available water for human use equates to only 0.78% of the Earth's total water supply.

The majority of available water is stored sub-surface in underground aquifers. Groundwater provides a low turbid source of water often naturally protected from contamination (Erdogan et al, 2019). Different aquifers may be susceptible to different contaminants such as arsenic or other dissolved solids, but when coupled with treatment techniques it provides a large and steady supply of water.

The most conventional source of water, contributing to 0.26% of total fresh water(Shiklomanov, 2000), is surface water. Consisting of rivers, lakes and reservoirs, surface water provides a steady and frequently replenished water source for most climates. However, whilst previously thought to be highly sustainable, external changes and human behaviour in the last few centuries threaten conventional methods of water supply. These external changes are population growth, economic growth and climate change.

1.1 Population and Economic Growth

Termed the 'great acceleration', the human world has experienced many rapid socio-economic changes since the 1950's (Steffen et al, 2015). Four of the many 'great acceleration' graphs are shown below, with each having an effect on global water consumption:

Figures 1-4, 'Great acceleration' graphs depicting the rapid changes in socio-economic factors, from 1750 to 2010 (Steffen, 2015)

Due to advancements in medicine, fertilisers, pesticides and fossil fuels, a combination of increased life expectancy and more readily available food and energy resulted in the sharp population increase shown in *Figure.1*. With higher population comes an expected increase in direct and indirect water demand. As well as for drinking/cleaning, large amounts of water will be used in the increased agricultural and industrial demand. A study on the change of water footprint from 2000 to 2050 by (Ertug Ercin, 2014) concluded that in some scenarios, global agricultural demand could increase by 112% whilst industrial demand up to 601%.

The rise in GDP has been credited to various reasons such as globalisation and the increase in international trade and co-operation (Crafts, 2004). The consequences this will have on water consumption may be less obvious. Whilst it is apparent higher GDP means more expenditure on industry, healthcare and other industries that will consume water, individual habits will change. People now have more money to spend on gardens, appliances such as dishwashers and more frequent bathing patterns. Diets will increase in size and are predicted to become higher in meat and protein content (Erb et al, 2009), with increased livestock such as cows and pigs creating high water demands themselves.

Some reports estimated that yearly global water withdrawal will increase from 4500 billion m³ in 2013 to 6900 billion m³ (McKinsey et al, 2009) in 2030. This large increase in withdrawal will have serious consequences on conventional water supplies if not carried out sustainably. *Figure.5* shows the major groundwater aquifers in the world (Gleeson et al, 2012). The colour scale represents the stress the aquifer faces due to extraction for human use. Aquifers with a groundwater footprint (GF/A_A) higher than 1 will deplete over time. Those sources that face the highest stress are highlighted at the bottom of the map, with the surrounding grey area the size the aquifer would have to be for its rate of replenishment to meet rate of extraction. Complete depletion of groundwater sources such as the Upper Ganges would be catastrophic on the large population that rely on them.

Figure 5, a map of groundwater aquifers and their corresponding groundwater footprints (Gleeson, 2012)

Surface water sources also face the possibility of depletion if local water demand becomes unsustainable. A current well-known case is the Aral sea, lying between Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. Before 1960, the Aral sea had an estimated volume of 1083 km³ of water (UN, 2017). However, due to extensive development of nearby land and soviet industrial use in the Aral sea basin, the volume fell by 1005 km³ in 2018 (Yang et al, 2020). If water withdrawal from the basin cannot be drastically cut down, many countries in the region will face serious consequences.

1.2 Effects of Climate Change

The exact effects of Global warming on the world is difficult to predict, although some trends are clear. Most countries in the mid to high latitudes will face rises in annual precipitation, with the frequency of multi-day precipitation events increasing (Easterling, 2000). *Figures 6 and 7*

depict the change in winter and summer precipitation from 1961 to 1995 in the United Kingdom (Osborn, 1999).

Figures 6 and 7, a map of precipitation change (mm) for December to February and June to August respectively from 1961-95. Large coloured dots show a larger increase in precipitation at that collection station, large white dots show a larger decrease in precipitation (Osborn, 1999)

In the winter, precipitation is increasing throughout the UK and more so in the west. According to a report on the drivers of UK floods (O'Donnell et al, 2020), increased precipitation as a result of climate change is the main driver. The extreme rainfall events caused by climate change, where rainfall is two to three times the monthly average, are not localised to certain areas. Nearly all the UK experienced at least one extreme rainfall event since 2014. This study also concluded that during the summer, the frequency of short but heavy rainfall events will increase. This results in flash floods occurring more often in the summer.

Simultaneously, total precipitation in the summer is decreasing. The ten hottest years of the UK since 1884 have all occurred since 2002 (Kendon et al, 2019), resulting in an increase in evapotranspiration (Richter, 2005). The combination of less rainfall and more evaporation will greatly decrease the replenishment rate of rivers and surface water sources, leading to potential droughts in summer months.

By increasing the frequency of low water flow in rivers, but also increasing flood events which draws in more contaminants to the water, the reliability of surface water as a source decreases (Arnell, 2006). Higher turbidity from floods and increased saline concentration in low flows reduce the water quality, requiring higher levels of treatment to be potable.

1.3 Urbanisation

Another driver on flood risks is urbanisation. Urbanisation is the process in which people from rural settings migrate to towns and cities, increasing the proportion of the urban population. Shown in the graph in *Figure.2*, urban population has dramatically risen since 1950, although as a direct result of a growing population as well as urbanisation. More development for housing, infrastructure and other necessities are required, continuously built from the existing urban area. This creates a large area of mostly impermeable surfaces, significantly increasing the volume of retained surface water compared to the pre-developed land composition. To prevent the build up of surface water, large drainage systems must be constructed to direct the stormwater away from the towns and cities, however this will often further concentrate the water in certain areas such as local rivers. In periods of extreme rainfall, the amount of stormwater directed from the city may be too high for either the urban or natural drainage infrastructure to contain, causing floods. Most drainage networks operate as a combined sewer, meaning the stormwater is collected and distributed in the same system as sewage. If flooding occurs, the overflow of stormwater is now contaminated and can introduce other issues such as disease to the water basin.

Coupled with an increase in extreme rainfall patterns due to climate change, the volume of stormwater that urban environments must handle may become a serious problem. High amounts of literature have been written on sustainable urban drainage systems (SuDS), yet there is still little progress on implementing these practices. A study by (O'Donnell, 2017) concluded that the most prevalent barriers to SuDS in their case study of Newcastle, UK were a reluctance to change/new approaches, lack of education/knowledge and a lack of funding.

1.4 Rainwater Harvesting

Rainwater harvesting (RWH) is an alternative water source which can help to combat the effects of climate change, population growth and urbanisation on water stress and flooding. Consisting of a catchment area for rain collection, a storage tank and various forms of filtration techniques (Hofman et al, 2014), RWH is a very simple technology that can be easily implemented throughout the world. Although it can be treated to meet drinking water standards, it is more common to provide non-potable water demand due to the reduced costs in filtration. RWH is not a new technology, with evidence of tanks for water collection dating as far back as 2600 BC (Pandey et al, 2003). Furthermore, its use in flood prevention has also been documented in India from 200 BC, with hydraulic earthworks constructed to store excess

floodwater from the river Ganga. However, for a technology as old as RWH, the amount of published literature on the topic has increased from 20 in the year 2000 to approximately 170 in 2010 (Hofman, 2014). Its use in preventing disastrous consequences from anthropogenic behaviour is becoming more apparent.

Some countries such as Australia have already undergone widespread implementation of rainwater harvesting. According to the Australian bureau of statistics, around 1.7 million households used a RWH system in 2015 (Campisano et al, 2017). Combined, this results in a saving of 156 GL of water. In Japan, introduction of RWH facilities has increased rapidly since the 1990's, with the accumulative number of facilities shown in *Figure.8*. Since 2012, Japan has continued to encourage the implementation of RWH with different government subsidies.

Figure 8, a graph of the rise in installed RWH facilities in Japan (Campisano et al, 2017)

In the UK, adapting rainwater harvesting has been much slower. Whilst, the government encourages the use and development of RWH, there was little financial or formal support like Japan or Australia (Ward et al, 2016). However, with the British standard for rainwater harvesting systems published in 2009 (BS8515:2009), the use of RWH is increasing and multiple RWH projects have been completed for commercial facilities.

1.5 Design

Many forms of RWH systems exist, the following system shown in *Figure.9* is a conventional style for residential collection and use. The roof of the building collects the precipitation which then flows into the rest of the system via guttering and downpipes. After being flushed and filtered from contaminants such as bacteria, the water enters a storage tank. Here, the water can be extracted when needed for the non-potable water demand of the house. If the tank overfills, excess water is spilt into the surroundings or existing stormwater drainage. If the tank cannot provide enough rainwater to meet demand, potable water will be withdrawn from the mains,

ensuring the resident will always have access to immediate water. Although commercial and large scale applications of RWH will have much larger variables, the process remains the same.

Figure 9, a conventional on-site RWH system where A =roof area, R_t =rainfall, H_t =filter losses, Q_t =tank inflow, O_t =tank overflow, V_t =occupied tank volume, S =total tank volume, Y_t = yield from tank, D_t =water demand and M_t =added mains water (Campisano et al, 2017).

The key parameters of RWH design that can significantly affect the performance are the tank volume and the catchment area. Catchment area can be less flexible as it is often limited to roof space, but the economic benefits and performance of the system is highly dependant on the tank volume. Larger tank volumes will retain larger amounts of rainfall, meeting more of the non-potable water demand and further reducing stormwater run-off. However, too large and the capital and operating costs will affect the economics of the system. Similarly, a small volume will greatly reduce costs but inhibit the performance.

The quality of the water treated from the rainwater system will depend on the treatment techniques used. Pre-treatment, rainwater will contain three types of contaminants: chemical, physical and microbiological (Hofman, 2014). Contaminants can enter the water in the storage tank, rooftop and in the clouds. Examples of contaminants can be total coliforms such as *E.coli*, heavy metals, organic pollutants and pH (Sazakli, 2007). In some developing countries, the quality of the treated rainwater must meet their drinking standards so it can be used as potable water. To meet this requirement, multiple treatment techniques must be used (Helmreich, 2009). A simple but effective procedure is 'first flush'; the initial run-off of rainwater after a dry day, which contains a higher volume of contaminants than usual, is discarded. After a simple screening to remove large objects, the next steps can include disinfection and filtration. Cheap disinfection can be achieved through chlorination, whereas filtration through a slow

sand filtration system. Other methods include solar technology to pasteurise the water, or bigger investments on membrane treatments.

Treating rainwater to meet potable water standards will often be expensive and conventional water sources will treat more water for cheaper. Therefore, rainwater finds a better use in non-potable water demand. Less filtration is required as the standards are not as strict, making a rainwater harvesting system more feasible.

1.5 Smart RWH

Conventional RWH systems can offer high performance in meeting water demand, yet are not very effective in reducing stormwater in extreme weather events. An active (smart) rainwater harvesting system provides the ability to constantly manage the volume of the tank available to store rainwater (Behzadian, 2018). Active RWH design is specified in the British standard BS8515:2009, citing three advantages to passive RWH systems: lower storage volumes, use as stormwater management is not constrained by Y/D ratio and the uncertainty of preparing for extreme events is removed. A maximum set-point is introduced in which any rainwater that surpasses the chosen volume will be emptied from the tank. This allows for extra storage space if an extreme rainfall event would occur. When the set-point is removed, the tank fills all the way up reducing the stormwater load on the drainage system. The set-point is only restarted once the downstream stormwater network is able to handle the extra spillage. The British standard gives two methods to control set point; weather forecasting and water level based.

In weather forecasting, the system is emptied if an extreme weather event is predicted to occur in 6 hours time. This time allows for the drainage network to process the spilt rainwater before the rainfall event occurs. Using weather forecasting ensures a higher yield/demand ratio as it only activates when a serious event is likely. If the system is instead based on the water level of the storage tank, the maximum set-point is always active unless currently in a large rainfall event. The amount of yield available will be much lower, although the system is now always prepared for unpredictable heavy storms.

To assess the effectiveness of smart RWH, total excess stormwater volume is calculated (Behzadian, 2018):

$$Total\ excess\ stormwater = \min \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T V_t^{SEx}}{\sum_{t=1}^T V_t^{NSEx}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

V_t^{SEx} and V_t^{NSEx} are the excess volumes of stormwater with and without RWH present. Equations 2 and 3 are followed if the sum of stormwater discharged to the combined sewer network (V_t^{SW}), spillage from the RWH tank (V_t^{TO}) and sanitary sewage already in the network (V_t^{SS}) exceeds the network capacity (Cap_{ws}):

$$V_t^{SEx} = V_t^{SW} + V_t^{TO} + V_t^{SS} - Cap_{ws} \quad (2)$$

$$V_t^{NSEx} = V_t^{SW} + V_t^{SS} - Cap_{ws} \quad (3)$$

Note that V_t^{SW} will be greater in (3) due to no stormwater being stored in the tank. If the network capacity is not exceeded, both values will be 0 resulting in no excess volumes of stormwater at that time step.

This metric investigates how the RWH performs under storm patterns. In sudden periods of high rainfall, high volumes of stormwater discharged into the drainage system may overload the system and cause a flood. Minor floods may not cause any damage or costs to the local area, however extreme rainfall periods may result in more serious consequences. High costs can arise from damage to property, agriculture and livestock, infrastructure problems and possibly damage to human life.

1.6 Economic viability

For a technology as old as RWH, its use as a water source is barely existent in many countries. This is mainly due to its economic viability when compared to more conventional sources such as surface water. High capital costs for plumbing relative to water savings can result in long payback times (Preece, 2006), whilst the use of pumps can result in lower energy-efficiency than alternatives (Vieira et al, 2014). However, more recent investigations using centralised models of large tanks supplying large demands have concluded RWH to be cost effective and feasible (Ward et al, 2012). Most literature failed to include the economic benefits that rainwater harvesting has on stormwater reduction. It is highly likely that including the reduction in flood damage in the economic analysis would prove RWH to be economically feasible.

1.7 Filton Airfield

The purpose of this report is to investigate the applicability of a rainwater harvesting system for the new residential and commercial development at Filton airfield, Bristol UK. The site has been developed by YTL, with the concept of sustainability considered throughout. NextGen, a

European project supporting circular water economy solutions in ten sites in 7 EU member states and the UK, have also been involved. There are currently plans for an integrated drainage and green infrastructure system, heat recovery from the sewer system and local capture of rainwater for non-potable use.

This report will assume a centralised collection system at the central Brabazon hanger, a world war II hanger which is set to be repurposed into an entertainment complex. The catchment area will be the hanger roof with an estimated area of 10,000 m². The rainwater will then be stored in a tank at the same location, to be transported to individual tanks found in each house. An alternative system, not included in this report, would be individual RWH systems at each house.

To assess the impact of a rainwater harvesting system on local water supply, a model must first be created. The behavioural model follows a simple mass balance using the different variables found in *Figure 1.1*. Using the yield before spillage (YBS) rule (Fewkes et al, 2000), the yield and tank volume at the current time step (i) follow:

$$Y_t = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} D_t \\ V_{t-1} + Q_t \end{matrix} \right. \quad (4)$$

$$V_t = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} V_{t-1} + Q_t - Y_t \\ S \end{matrix} \right. \quad (5)$$

The Yield is the volume of water withdrawn from the storage tank to meet the demand. In the YBS model, if there is enough water in the tank then yield will equate to demand. Otherwise, yield will be the water volume of the tank, which is lower than demand. Once yield has been calculated, the new water volume is found from *Equation 1.2*. As the water cannot exceed the tank's capacity, excess rainwater is spilt from the tank.

The alternative model uses yield after spillage (YAS). Here, the excess water is spilt before the yield is calculated, giving rise to the following equations:

$$Y_t = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} D_t \\ V_{t-1} \end{matrix} \right. \quad (6)$$

$$V_t = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} V_{t-1} + Q_t - Y_t \\ S - Y_t \end{matrix} \right. \quad (7)$$

Models using a YBS approach will often overestimate the performance of the RWH, inflating indicators such as water saving efficiency (Zhang et al, 2020). Conversely, YAS models will underestimate performance. This is due to the YAS models spilling water before yield is taken, reducing the effective storage capacity.

1.8 Evaluating results

To evaluate the results, three performance indicators will be calculated. The following indicators were taken from existing literature (Zhang et al, 2020):

- Water saving efficiency (WS) – This value determines how much of the non-potable water demand (D) is met by the rainwater yield (Y). What makes a good WS efficiency is highly dependant on many factors. If the catchment area is small, the value may be quite low even though all rain is being captured. Likewise, if water demand is high the efficiency will be small. As WS efficiency is being used mostly to optimise the RWH system, it will be good if it is higher than the other tank sizes or set-points.

$$WS = \frac{\sum Y}{\sum D} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

- Storm capture efficiency (SC) – This indicator calculates how much of the total rainwater is captured by the RWH system. It is useful to assess how effective the system is at reducing the stormwater load on the drainage network. A is the catchment area, R the total rainfall and φ the run-off co-efficient.

$$SC = \frac{\sum Y}{\sum(A \times R \times \varphi) / 1000} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

- Reliability (r) – The reliability of a RWH system is the proportion of time steps (hours or days) of non-potable demand that is met by rainwater only. If reliability is 100%, rainwater harvesting could be used as the primary source of non-potable water supply. Whilst not as important as the previous indicators for this report, it allows for an extra variable for comparison. U is the time steps where yield meets or exceeds demand, N is the total number of time steps.

$$r = \frac{U}{N} \times 100\% \quad (10)$$

An important question that must be asked is what is meant by feasibility. Is the RWH system feasible if it can be successfully used as a primary source of all non-potable demands? Is the system feasible if it makes a profit? Or is it simply feasible if there is a good enough environmental benefit and relax on local water stress. For the sake of this report, we will consider the last two. It is not expected for rainwater harvesting to be the primary source, only assist other sources and improve the sustainability of water supply.

2 Project Planning and Design

2.1 Aims and Objectives

The overall aim of this project is to conclude whether rainwater harvesting can be a feasible complimentary water supply for the Filton development. To meet this aim, many objectives must be completed:

- A stochastic model that simulates rainfall similar to real data should be developed. This will allow for greater testing of the RWH system under different rainfall patterns.
- A behavioural model must be created to quantify the behaviour of the RWH tank over the chosen time period, using the simulated rainfall and realistic water demand.
- Parameters of the model will be optimised to achieve the best results. This will improve its feasibility.
- Finally, the optimum model will be analysed using economic metrics, assessing the financial viability.

2.2 Difficulties from COVID-19

Due to the lockdown caused by the COVID-19 virus, this research project could not be completed to the full extent it was hoped to. A data restriction policy from the 17th of March meant there was no time for simulations optimising the rainfall threshold that activates the set-point. Data could not be collected on the stormwater capacity or sewage volumes of local drainage systems, hindering the analysis of set-point. Furthermore, data on the operating and capital costs needed to investigate the economics of the RWH system could not be obtained. A look at the differences a de-centralised or semi-centralised model would have on its viability compared was intended. Finally, an updated rainfall model that accounted for errors discovered in the analysis could not be finished.

As all the above were important to conclude the feasibility of RWH, each were still discussed in detail in section 4. How each were expected to impact the system, as well as comparison to literature for the economic analysis, have been included. Whilst a conclusion on feasibility has been reached, it is important to note that it is not confirmed as there was not enough evidence generated from this report.

3 Model Development

3.1 Behavioural model

To create the RWH model, Python software was used. The equations for the **YAS model were** used to draft a logical flowchart depicted in *Figure.10*.

Figure 10, the flowchart created to visualise the behaviour of the RWH tank

A maximum setpoint for the tank was added to improve the systems capability for stormwater control. This setpoint would only apply when the rainfall is below a chosen threshold, therefore in heavy rainfall the tank would fill before spilling. Using simple If loops, this was translated into the python code.

Instead of using only **YAS or YBS**, the coding allows for a switch between the two. This provided a potential avenue for analysis to investigate how each would affect the performance of the system.

3.2 Rainfall

Whilst the behavioural model used simple mass balances, accurate rainfall is difficult to simulate. Historical rainfall data can be a useful input if collected over a large time period (at least 30 years), and at regular intervals such as hourly. If the data series is too short, the results will not be accurate enough. If monthly or daily rainfall values are used, the results will again be less accurate and performance indicators will appear worse than they should (Zhang et al,

2020). The available historical data was collected from the online platform Weather Underground, displaying rainfall from 2008 to 2018 in the Bristol area. The rainfall was measured in daily intervals. To increase the length of data and frequency of collection from this existing data, a separate model must be created.

Due to the stochastic nature of rainfall, a stochastic model was used rather than a deterministic one. In a deterministic model, the dependant variables are determined only by the existing parameters of the model (Rey, 2015). **Conversely, stochastic models are more random and create probability distributions rather than concrete values. Creating a deterministic model of rainfall would not just be time consuming, but extremely difficult. Rainfall is dependant on a large range of factors, to include each factor accurately would be impossible with the time and resource constraints of this investigation. Instead, using a stochastic model to create probability distributions of rainfall based on historical data seemed more appropriate.**

The historical data was input into Python and fitted into a histogram plot, before being applied to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The histogram is shown in *Figure.11*:

Figures 11, a histogram plot showing the distribution of the size of rainfall events from 2008 to 2018

As the K-S test was used to look at the distribution of rainfall magnitude, all days with no rainfall were emitted. This test compared the data to three different distribution plots (exponential, lognormal and normal), returning a ‘p value’ to indicate which distribution type fitted the data best. An exponential plot returned the highest value therefore, the data was assumed to best follow an exponential pattern. As well as a p value, the K-S test returned two useful parameters; location and scale. Location determines the mean value for a generated data series, whilst scale determines how stretched the data is across the y-axis.

With the data now fit to a distribution, the code to create a new hourly rainfall pattern could be written. A While and If loop was used; while the current time step was within the time frame (flexible and set by the user), a probability function decided whether rain would occur at that time. This probability was calculated from the number of wet and dry days in the whole set of rainfall data. If the function returned 'no rain' then no rainfall fell in that hour. If there was rain, another function (random variates function) would create a rainfall value from an exponential curve using the calculated location and scale parameters. The probability the rainfall would be heavy or light was dependant on this exponential curve. Once the desired number of hours had been simulated, a new file with the rainfall was created, nearly ready for use in the behavioural model.

Now that rainfall was generated for a chosen number of hours, it had to be converted into tank inflow (Q) before its input to the behavioural model of the tank. The equation below, obtained from BS8515:2009, was used:

$$Q_t = A \times R_t \times \varphi \quad (11)$$

A was the collection area of the central hanger (10,000 m²), R the rainfall at that time step and φ the run-off co-efficient. The run-off co-efficient accounted for the proportion of rainwater that remained on the roof. φ was assumed to be 0.95, given for a pitched roof with profiled metal sheeting (BS8515:2009). Another co-efficient that could be included in this equation is the filter co-efficient. This parameter would account for the rainwater lost when passing through the filter. However, as these losses are minimal to begin with and will soon vary dependant on the quality of the rainwater, it was not included.

To validate that the model produced the right amount of rainfall, the cumulative rainfall was compared to an average of the area. Since 2008, the average yearly rainfall was approximately 798 mm, with a range from 584 mm to 1135 mm. This compared similarly to the model, with the eventual chosen rainfall pattern producing 707 mm of rainfall in the year. In hindsight, validating the model should have compared the seasonal changes and periodicity of the rainfall. This was a major limitation which was only realised after the 17th of march. Months such as December or November which would usually experience large volumes of rainfall, experience the same as August or July in the simulation. If more time was allowed to alter this coding, further research would be taken into how this could be adapted. The changes to the stochastic model may have been complex and resulted in a complete change, such as using a Poisson model with pulses (Rodriguez-Iturbe et al, 1987). Alternatively, it may have been simple such

as calculating the average probability of dry and wet days for each month instead of the whole data set.

3.2 Demand

The final step was to simulate a pattern of water usage for 278 houses in the Filton development. Whilst not as random as rainfall, demand is still highly dependent on many factors such as time of day, day of the week, resident habits and even the gender or age of the residents. Rather than expend large amounts of effort and time into creating a model to predict Filton's water demand, a pre-developed MATLAB programme called SIMDEUM was used.

Created by KWR in conjunction with the Dutch water companies, SIMDEUM is a complex tool which generates demand patterns for different household appliances. It uses a .SPG file with a mix of pre-determined values and data input by the user to create .stats files of water demand in the week and at the weekend. Using these files, the programme can then simulate water demand up to a week for each house stated.

Although the percentage of one person or multiple households is known, the statistics of the residents in each house cannot be accurately given as the site is still in development. For the initial analysis the demo files created by KWR were only slightly tweaked. The composition of household size was changed to 25.5 % single person, 33.8% two person and 40.7% more than two. The division of age, employment and other factors were left the same. The impact this will have on the accuracy of demand is likely to be minimal due to similarities between Dutch and English culture. If more time was allowed on data collection, changes to the demand data may have been analysed using existing census data of the Bristol area. It is possible the census data is just as inaccurate due to being nine years old and with the potential to be very different to the actual statistics of the Filton development.

Two simulations were completed for demand, one consisting of just a toilet for water use and another including a washing machine as well. It was thought that an increase in demand may affect different parameters such as optimum tank size, and where the set-point should lie. The yearly demand without the washing machine was 12652 m³, whilst a washing machine increased this to 15412 m³. The two sets of data were exported from SIMDEUM and either could be used as the demand output for the Python code. As demand was simulated for only a week, the Python code repeated the pattern for a variable number of weeks. This means

seasonal changes and holidays are neglected, with the demand pattern assumed to remain constant.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Optimisation

Before serious analysis into RWH on Filton was carried out, the model needed to be optimised to ensure the outcome accurately showed the potential of RWH. This involved analysis of the tank size, difference between YAS and YBS, maximum setpoint at low rainfall and optimising this rainfall threshold. The same demand pattern was used throughout, keeping the results accurate. Although, different rainfall patterns were used which will be explained.

4.1.1 Tank Size

To investigate the effects of storage capacity on the system, six different tank volumes were included. Each tank volume was calculated from five dimensionless storage fractions (Sf), using:

$$Sf = S/A \times R \quad (12)$$

Chosen storage fractions were 0.002, 0.0015, 0.001, 0.00075, 0.0005 and 0.00025. Whilst past studies such as (Fewkes et al, 2000) use fractions in the range of 1.08 to 0.0015, initial simulations showed little change above a fraction of 0.0015. It is likely this is due to the lack of periodicity in the rainfall data. As the stochastic model of rainfall does not account for this periodicity, historical rainfall data was also analysed.

The following graphs show the effect of storage fraction on water saving efficiency (WS), stormwater capture efficiency (SC) and reliability. Figures 12, 14 and 16 use a demand of only one toilet in each house, whilst Figures 13, 15 and 17 also include a washing machine. Using the simulated demand from SIMDEUM, the washing machine results in an extra 2850 m³ of water demand. As expected, all three indicators increased with tank size. Each data series followed a strong logarithmic trend, confirmed by their R² co-efficients shown in Table.1.

Figures 12 to 17, graphs of three performance indicators against storage fraction, without and with a washing machine respectively.

Table.1, R² co-efficients for each performance indicator with each model type

R ² Co-efficient			
Model	WS efficiency	SC efficiency	Reliability
YAS	0.9339	0.934	0.9604
YBS	0.944	0.9441	0.9716
YAS (WM)	0.9126	0.9126	0.9477
YBS (WM)	0.9232	0.9232	0.9787

At high tank sizes, the effect of YBS and YAS was negligible. Either one of the models could be used and this would have no impact on the results. However, as tank size began to decrease, the difference between each model increased. For example, in *Figure.12* the range between YBS and YAS was only 0.03% at Sf=0.002. When storage fraction was decreased to 0.00025, the range increased to 8.48%. This will result in large uncertainty that must be considered when analysing lower tank sizes.

When demand consisted of only a toilet, the maximum water saving efficiency that could be achieved if all rainfall was utilised was 53.47%. For a storage fraction of 0.002 (14.14 m³), WS efficiency was close to maximum with 53.42%. This is due to only 9.66 m³ of water being spilt from the tank over the year. A storage fraction of 0.0015 (10.6 m³) showed little change with a WS efficiency between 53.14% and 52.85%. It is when a fraction of 0.001 (7.07 m³) is used that WS efficiency begins to quickly drop. Efficiency falls to between 51.69% and 50.71%. Whilst this may not seem significant, this is a loss of between 217,000 and 340,000 L when compared to a fraction of 0.002. Any lower than 0.001 and the efficiency drops significantly, ruling out a tank size of below 7 m³.

For stormwater capture efficiency and reliability, a fraction of 0.001 also seemed to be the point at which the indicator begins to drop substantially. Whilst less apparent for reliability (a difference of between 1.43% and 0.8%), SC efficiency dropped between 3.2% and 5%. This means a tank size of 7.07 m³ could prevent up to 335 m³ less rainwater reaching the stormwater drainage every year.

When the demand increased to include a washing machine, the trends for each indicator remained the same. WS efficiency decreased for all tank sizes, as the large increase in demand was not met with an increase in rainfall. Reliability also decreased as demand was larger than tank water volume more often than before. However, the SC efficiency increased as the larger demand meant there would be less water volume in the tank therefore less water spilt.

The optimum tank size, using the above performance indicators, lies between 7 m^3 and 10 m^3 . Any higher than 10 m^3 , the extra capital and operating costs of a larger storage tank will yield little benefit to the efficiency and reliability of the system. Smaller than 7 m^3 , the performance will drastically decrease and accuracy of results will become uncertain due to YAS and YBS differences. Using rainfall data from the stochastic model will therefore lie around 9 m^3 .

4.1.2 Tank Size with Similar Historical Data

To observe the effect periodicity and seasonal changes might have on tank size, the raw historical data was also used as an input to the behavioural model. It was believed these factors could significantly increase the optimal storage fraction of the system. The year 2018 was chosen for the simulation, as yearly rainfall was only 0.8 mm less than the simulated rainfall. The rainfall pattern for the year is shown in *Figure.18*.

Figure 18, Rainfall pattern in Bristol throughout the year 2018.

Eight storage fractions were chosen this time, starting from 0.0015 (an optimum fraction using the simulated rainfall), 0.0025, 0.005, 0.0075, 0.01, 0.015, 0.025 and 0.05. Their effect on WS efficiency, SC efficiency and reliability are shown in Figures 19 to 24. As the rainfall and demand were now measured in daily quantities, the performance indicators are expected to be inaccurate by a maximum of 2%.

Figures 19 to 24, graphs of three performance indicators against storage fraction using historical data, without and with a washing machine respectively.

It is already clear that the stated optimum storage fraction of 0.0015 does not remain optimum for the historical data. Whilst previously providing around 53% of demand, it now contributes between 30.59% and 10.80%. Assuming the highest value of 30.59%, this change relates to a 2813 m³ drop in demand met. The same trend applies to SC efficiency (a decrease in the range

of 41.6% and 78.63%). As the time scale is now daily, and an Sf of 0.0015 is 10 m^3 , it is impossible for daily yield to meet daily demand using a YAS model. If the historical data were hourly, a reliability of higher than 0% would be calculated, although it will still be a low figure.

The reason for this large shift to higher storage fractions is all due to the seasonal changes and periodicity. In the simulated rainfall, each hour has a probability of 53.25% that no rain will fall. Even if the hour before has extremely high rainfall of 40 mm, the next hour may be completely dry. Furthermore, the model uses this same probability throughout the whole year, predicting a similar pattern of rainfall in winter and summer. Comparing *Figure.18* and *Figure.25*, you can clearly see this effect.

Figure 25, Simulated rainfall for a year.

Due to the nature of the model, there are no days that have no rainfall and the largest volume of water that the RWH system could collect in a single day was 40 m^3 . This results in a very steady inflow of rainwater which very rarely exceeds the capacity of a 14.4 m^3 tank. In reality, the system may go weeks without any rainfall or may be subject to 250 m^3 in one day. Therefore, a larger tank will be needed to store rainfall in high intensity days.

The optimum storage fraction now lies within the range of 0.01 and 0.025. Whilst higher than 0.025 will still increase the RWH performance by a reasonable amount, the increase in tank size from 170.7 m^3 is likely to increase operating and capital costs dramatically (more detail later in the report) Tank sizes lower than 70.7 m^3 (Sf = 0.01) will significantly decrease the performance of the system, whilst only marginally saving capital and operational costs.

4.1.3 Tank Size with Varied Historical Data

The purpose of the simulated rainfall was to analyse the system under multiple rainfall patterns. Therefore, more than one year of historical data was investigated. Whilst 2018 produced a similar amount of rainfall to the model, the wettest available year (2012) produced 429 mm more and the driest year (2010) 122 mm less. Their rainfall patterns are shown below in *Figures. 26 and 27:*

Figure 26, Rainfall pattern in Bristol throughout the year 2012.

Figure 27, Rainfall pattern in Bristol throughout the year 2010.

Using the wettest and driest years could show the greatest variance in tank optimisation. The same eight tank volumes were used rather than storage fractions, as the differing yearly rainfall alters the volume from each fraction. Only the demand pattern excluding a washing machine

was used this time. As both demand patterns show the same trend when changing tank size, this would save time.

Figures 28 to 33, graphs of three performance indicators against storage fraction using historical data, for 2010 and 2012 respectively

Whilst there is a clear difference in performance, it is more important to look at the difference in optimum range. The reason for different WS efficiencies is due to more rainfall falling in the year 2012, resulting in more demand met. Likewise, SC efficiencies will decrease in 2012 when there is more rainfall falling, making it harder to capture the same percentage.

For SC efficiency, the optimum tank size will still lie in the range of 70.7 m³ and 170.7 m³. In terms of reliability, the optimum will lie between 35.3 m³ and 106 m³ for 2010, whilst for 2012 this increases to 70.7 m³ and 170.7 m³. As 2010 was the driest year, it makes sense that the best tank size decreases. As there is less rainfall to collect and smaller peaks, tank size does not need to be large. Conversely, RWH systems in the high rainfall periods of 2012 will perform better when the tank can store more rainwater.

Looking at the WS efficiency, the range will fall between the 35.3 m³ tank and possibly a volume of 150 m³. However in 2012, it is difficult to decide where the optimum will be as the efficiency still increases by approximately 8% between 177 m³ and 353 m³. To better decide which is the more effective tank volume, financial savings and costs must be considered.

4.1.4 Costs and Savings with Tank Size

To further optimise tank volume, more simulations were carried out with tank sizes within and slightly outside the stated optimum range. *Table.2* shows the yield of each simulation, a useful value as it equals the volume of potable water saved over the year.

Table.2, Yield values for different tank sizes

Tank Size	Without Washing Machine		With Washing Machine	
	YAS Yield (m ³)	YBS Yield (m ³)	YAS Yield (m ³)	YBSwm Yield (m ³)
71	4,530	5094	4,810	5,547
90	4,864	5344	5,188	5,783
110	5,155	5560	5,500	5,963
130	5413	5760	5757	6135
150	5616	5933	5942	6275
170	5815	6073	6118	6,393

According to a leaflet distributed by Bristol water, they will charge £1.2669 for a cubic metre of water in 2020/21 (Bristol water, 2020). As this is the price of water and not the cost to treat potable water, the financial savings calculated using this value will be more inflated than reality. This price will account for extra costs to Bristol water such as plumbing and pumping the water, which would also be a cost for the rainwater. However, finding an exact value for the cost difference between potable and rainwater proved difficult. Therefore, the standard price given by Bristol water was used in the analysis.

To assess the costs associated with an increase in tank volume, the price of large galvanised steel water storage tanks from a nearby company (Tanks Direct) in Minehead, Somerset were used. Whilst the company provides specialised rainwater harvesting tanks and systems for

domestic use, the tank capacities did not exceed 20 m³. Operating costs were assumed to be negligible. The pumps and energy requirements would be the same regardless of tank size, due to the same volume of water being pumped out for demand. However, costs associated with the required space of each tank may increase the initial capital costs. The 72 m³ tank occupied 23 m² whilst the 150 m³ tank occupied 65.6 m². The storage tank prices are shown in *Figure.34*:

Figure 34, Price of five different tanks from Tanks Direct

The price of each tank follows the same increase except the 72 m³ tank. For a better analysis this price was changed using Excel's LINEST function, with both included in *Table.3*:

Table.3, price, yield, potable water savings and the price/savings difference for different tank volumes

Tank Volume (m ³)	Price	YAS Yield (m ³)	YBS Yield (m ³)	YBS Savings	YAS Savings	Maximum Difference	Minimum Difference
54	£2,414	4106.66	4841.00	£6,133	£5,203	£3,719	£2,788
72	£3,198	4550.01	5107.92	£6,471	£5,764	£3,273	£2,566
100	£3,408	5016.85	5460.46	£6,918	£6,356	£3,510	£2,948
150	£4,434	5615.70	5933.23	£7,517	£7,115	£3,083	£2,681
200	£5,892	6041.44	6265.96	£7,938	£7,654	£2,046	£1,762
72 (adapted)	£2,910	4550.01	5107.92	£6,471	£5,764	£3,561	£2,854

Dependant on which behavioural model used, the optimum tank size will be different. Using the conservative YAS model, the optimum peak in *Figures.35* and *36* lie around the 100 m³ mark. However, for a YBS model the optimum peak will lie further to the left of the chosen range. To further improve the reliability of the total savings, other savings such as the reduced damage from flooding should be considered. In large storm events, larger tanks will store greater amounts of the rainfall and reduce the sudden load on the stormwater drainage. This results in less damage costs on the local council, which can be anywhere in the range of

thousands to millions of pounds. Flood reduction is discussed in greater detail in section 4.1.5. Because of this, the optimum tank size will be chosen as 100 m³.

Figures 35 and 36, A graph of Potable water savings-cost for different tank sizes, without and with a washing machine respectively.

4.1.5 Set Point

To analyse the effect of a maximum set-point when rainfall is low, five different points were analysed. These would be 100% of total tank size (no set point), 90%, 80%, 70% and 60%. The rainfall threshold was kept at 10 mm throughout. As the simulated data now proved to be unreliable and inaccurate, the historical data from 2018 was used again. With a tank size of 100 m³, the results are as follows:

Figures 37 to 42, graphs of three performance indicators against set-point, without and with a washing machine respectively

Using the YBS model, a lower set-point caused a reduction in performance, although only a small one. Excluding a washing machine and with a set-point at 60 %, the WS efficiency drops only by 2.56 %. SC efficiency falls by 4.79 % and reliability by 0.82 %. Conversely, the YAS model showed no change in performance. Unlike previous results, the difference between the two behavioural models decreased with a lower set-point.

It was anticipated that including a set-point would only hinder the performance indicators, as the main indicator that would show improvement is the total excess stormwater. It is difficult to quantify this metric due to a high uncertainty of how much damage would be caused. Many factors come into play that would be near impossible to model. One option is to investigate past floods; how much excess stormwater volume was released and what were the associated costs. By using multiple examples, a correlation between stormwater volume and cost could be drafted and used in this analysis. However due to the project data restriction imposed by COVID-19, this was not possible.

Simulations using rainfall data from the Bristol area in 2012 would have better highlighted the reduction of total excess stormwater. The rainfall pattern for the year is shown in *Figure.26*. In the month of December, daily rainfall reached a peak of 42 mm, nearly double the peak in 2018. Running more simulations using this data could have led to a lower optimum set-point that could greatly reduce the effects of heavy rainfall like this. However, a low set-point to reduce heavy storm damage would result in higher losses of yield in dry years and months. Further simulations using years with low rainfall would have helped answer this.

Finally, another step to optimise the use of a set-point would be to consider seasonal changes in the set-point. This is the basis of smart RWH, by using rainfall data from the same month of each year, optimum set-points for each month could be calculated. The behavioural model could then be updated to change the set-point depending on which month is currently being simulated. This would mean more water is stored in the tank in dry months, whereas the set-point is lowered in wet months to prepare for possible storm events.

4.1.6 Rainfall Threshold

Analysing rainfall threshold would have likely been similar to set-point. When the threshold is increased, the WS efficiency, SC efficiency and reliability would have decreased. This is because the set-point will be active for longer and more water will be spilt. However, when severe rain patterns occurred, the tank would store rainwater when rainfall at the peak of the storm rather than before. This means the tank would reduce stormwater at the time of the storm where the network is facing its highest load. This would result in an increase, possibly significant, in total excess stormwater. Eventually, when rainfall threshold is too high, the set-point will always be present and the system will act like a conventional RWH system although with a reduced volume.

With the rainfall threshold decreased, the three performance indicators would improve as the set-point is activated less. Whilst this would increase savings from yield, the set-point would kick in early in a severe storm and only reduce load when the network can already handle it. This lack of protection disregards the point of the smart RWH, and when decreased lower the system will again just act like a conventional one.

4.2 Feasibility of RWH in Filton

Whilst some basic financial analysis was used to optimise the tank volume, this is not enough to make a justified decision on its applicability in Filton. As no more data and simulations can be collected, this section will have to mostly be theoretical. However, it will look at the many different methods and metrics that can be used to decide on RWH's feasibility. As mentioned before, there are multiple ways to judge feasibility. The following will look at the system's ability to make a profit or induce savings.

4.2.1 Capital and Operating Costs

The actual capital and operating costs associated with the RWH system will be far from the tank cost only. The cost of installation such as hiring multiple contractors, permits and instrumentation control were never considered in the optimisation as they are likely similar regardless of tank size. The same applies to the energy requirements for pumping and monitoring. To assess RWH cost in relation to mains water, they will have to be considered. Most reports investigating RWH looked at a de-centralised approach with small tanks in each house. However, some articles explored the operating costs and all capital costs for centralised storage tanks. *Figure.43* shows a breakdown on investment costs for different storage types in Amsterdam's Schiphol airport (Kuller et al, 2017).

Figure 43, a breakdown on investment costs for a RWH system at Schiphol airport, Amsterdam (Kuller et al, 2017)

The graph shows different options that the article considered, from supplying the whole airport using maximum rainwater harvesting (I) to supplying only the central terminal with maximum harvesting (III). Option II is likely the most similar to the Filton case study, involving only a roof catchment area for the central terminal only. However, the percentages will differ to Filton as the annual demand in option II is approximately 500,000 m³. The main takeaway from this graph is that the cost of the tank itself may only be between 10 and 50% of all capital costs.

Building the supply network can sometimes meet or exceed the tank costs, this will also apply to Filton airfield. Whilst the main centralised tank may cost £3408, a separate distribution network to each house must be built that contains only rainwater, as it cannot mix with mains water.

Collection infrastructure will not apply if the Brabazon hangar roof is the catchment area. The costs of installing a treatment system however will remain. Explained in the introduction, rainwater does not meet the required national levels of contamination for use. Even for non-potable use in toilets and laundry, filtration is required. However, the quality of filtration achieved is dependent on the treatment process used. There are multiple options that can be considered with varying operational and capital costs. For example, using activated carbon and silver ions in a settling tank is effective enough but will require routine maintenance (Adler et al. 2011). Simple sand filtration is inexpensive and common, although the fluctuating yield of rainwater may reduce its effectiveness (Fewster et al. 2004). Each treatment process has its own costs regarding initial capital, frequent maintenance or operation. These must be included in the economic analysis for a reliable conclusion.

Whilst initial capital is important, operating costs are just as necessary to consider. Pumping and electrical costs were not considered in optimisation as they are the same (or very similar) regardless of tank size. Operating costs can also include maintenance. This may be cleaning of the tank and equipment, replacing damaged or old parts, locating and fixing bursts and frequent testing of the water to ensure safe quality. Maintenance ensures the system is working as effectively as possible and that the output water meets national standards. Although applying to small RWH tanks on a domestic scale, *Table.4* highlights different parts and their life expectancy before replacement is expected (Roebuck et al, 2012). Items such as the pump, filter and valves will be much larger therefore much more expensive.

Table 4, examples of maintenance costs for a RWH system

Maintenance item	Frequency	Cost
Replace storage tank	Long life expectancy so assumed to remain functional over analysis time horizon	–
Replace mains top-up solenoid valve	Every 7.5 years	£60 for valve, £50 installation fee = £110
Replace pump	Every 10 years	£350 for pump, £75 installation fee = £425
Replace mains top-up level switch	Every 12.5 years	£20 for switch, £50 installation fee = £70
Replace coarse filter	Every 15 years	£300 for filter, £50 installation fee = £350
Replace electronic controls	Every 15 years	£140 for controls, £50 installation fee = £190
Replace internal plastic pipes	Every 35 years	Total cost (parts + labour) = £250

4.2.2 Methods of Financial Evaluation

One tool to analyse RWH at Filton is to make a life cycle cost analysis (Amos et al, 2016). To carry this out, data would have to be obtained on the costs and benefits of the RWH system throughout its 'life'. In this case, life refers to the initial investment in infrastructure and equipment of the tanks till the end of its expected operation. The capital costs given above apply to year 0, whereas the operational/maintenance costs and yield savings apply to each year after. The costs and benefits of future years will be discounted using net present discount factors. To understand the results, multiple calculations would have been made. The following list is adapted from (Amos et al, 2016):

- **Benefit cost ratio (BCR)**; this is the ratio of the sum of discounted costs over the sum of discounted benefits (13). The discount factor, $(1 + i)^t$, is a function of the interest rate. This metric would compare all the capital and operating costs of the RWH system to the total savings from the reduction of mains water. The smaller the ratio, the better. Any higher than one, the system is not feasible for the set number of operational years as the costs outweigh the benefits.

$$BCR = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^N \frac{C_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^N \frac{B_t}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (13)$$

- **Levelized cost (LC)**; this is a useful tool to compare the cost of making non-potable water against mains water. Shown in (14), the total cost of the project up to the chosen year is divided by the total volume of yield. If the RWH feasibility is dependant on economics only, then this value must be lower than the levelized cost of the mains water. If it is higher, then the mains water is cheaper to produce therefore should be used instead of rainwater. Therefore, it would not be a feasible alternative to current potable water. If the levelized cost was similar or only slightly higher, but other economic variables including the reduction in flood damage were promising, a slightly high LC might be acceptable.

$$LC = \frac{NPV \text{ of the project } (\pounds)}{Total \text{ Yield } (m^3)} \quad (14)$$

- **Payback Period (PP)**; this calculation is used often throughout RWH literature to discuss economic feasibility. It is simply the number of years it takes for the RWH system to pay back the initial capital costs. Lower capital costs or significantly greater yield savings than operational costs will reduce payback period. It was difficult to find payback periods of similar systems that used only one tank rather than multiple for each house. For a system with a tank in every house, payback periods were often high. A study on RWH in the UK (Roebuck et al.

2012) determined their payback period to be approximately 27 years, although when discount rates were applied the system would never pay back the initial investment. However, in the nearby University of Exeter, YAS simulations were carried out for a single tank to meet 1,353 m³ of demand (Ward et al, 2010). It was calculated that the investment on their optimum 9m³ tank would be paid back in 7 years without discount rates. Therefore, it is possible that the RWH system proposed in this report may have a low payback period or never return its initial investments. Using the tank cost only and yield savings, payback period would be less than a year; clearly not correct. Although, it is also important to note that these experiments never accounted for flood prevention.

Each calculation could have helped to understand whether the RWH would pay for itself over time. If the BCR was below 1, levelized cost was similar or lower than mains water and payback period was within an acceptable time (≈ 20 years) then the system would be deemed financially feasible.

4.2.3 With or Without Laundry

Throughout the report demand patterns excluding and including washing machines were used. The purpose of this was to identify any differences that might arise between the two either in performance or economic analysis. It was thought that the optimum tank size and set-point might increase significantly when laundry was considered. This would then alter the capital and operating costs which might impact whether it is feasible or not. However, the optimum tank volume remained similar (shown in *Figures.35* and *36*), meaning the only difference would be the increased savings. Therefore, it is best to use the rainwater for laundry as well as toilet use as this will increase the yearly savings and decrease payback period, BCR and LC.

4.2.4 De-centralised Model

As mentioned in the project planning, it was intended for the model to also simulate a de-centralised system where each house had its own RWH tank and roof as its catchment area. This would have brought many differences to the current set-up as the simulations look at individual houses. Catchment areas would decrease to around 20 m², yearly demand to ≈ 45 and 55 m³ and run-off co-efficient to 0.9 as the roof composition is no longer metal sheeting. Multiple demand patterns must be generated as the individual houses varied greatly. Some were four person households with greater demand but larger catchment areas, others were apartment buildings with smaller rainfall catchment. The objective was to compare the performance

indicators between the two models. It was likely that both a centralised and de-centralised system would display similar reliability, WS and SC efficiencies. Therefore, an emphasis on the financial evaluation and costs would decide if one, both or none of the models were feasible.

This type of system would reduce the need for a second water distribution network for rainwater only. This significantly reduces the large capital costs required for the infrastructure, such as laying all the pipework. Furthermore, no large space is required for a 100m³ (or larger) tank as the smaller individual tanks will fit in the attics or underground at each house.

However, the maintenance costs will greatly increase. Assuming 278 RWH tanks for each house/apartment, 278 filtration systems will have to be continuously maintained to a high standard. The time taken for a worker to monitor the quality of a centralised tank versus 278 tanks will be significantly lower. Conversely, if one tank faces serious problems and must be worked on, only that house is affected. If the centralised tank cannot distribute water due to electronic or equipment failure, the whole site will be affected. There are benefits and drawbacks to both types of systems.

4.2.5 Semi-centralised Model

Analysis into a combination of the two system types was also planned. In this scenario, the Filton site would be split into zones with a medium sized RWH tank for each zone. This idea was based on the University of Exeter site (Ward et al, 2010), where 173 homes were split into thirteen zones. The catchment area of each zone would be the surface area of all the included roofs. If needed, the Brabazon hangar could have also acted as a catchment area.

Dividing the houses into zones would have allowed for a higher degree of optimisation. There is control over which houses use which RWH tank and the size of each individual tank. Lots of analysis could have been used to find the ideal zone allocation, with WS and SC efficiencies dependant on the sizes of tanks used. It is likely that this level of optimisation would mean this system is more effective than the other two. Operating costs will be higher than a single tank, although the increased performance would generate greater savings. However, without the simulation results it is not possible to confirm this.

4.2.6 Is it Feasible?

Rainwater harvesting cannot be the primary supply of all non-potable water, not enough rain falls. But will it pay for itself and bring a profit? Without concrete economic analysis it is hard

to confirm, but it is likely. Little maintenance is required for a centralised system, and the predicted yield savings used a very low-priced mains water for comparison. The UK average can be twice the amount Bristol water offer. Tank size is relatively cheap however, the uncertainty lies in operating costs and other capital investment. Most related literature stating rainwater harvesting is not economically feasible use individual house roofs for the catchment area. The use of the Brabazon hangar roof provides a much larger catchment area, increasing the rainwater available and allowing for the RWH system to create enough yield to be feasible. Therefore looking at the economics only, rainwater harvesting will likely only be feasible if the hangar roof can be used as a catchment area.

The benefit of using a smart rainwater harvesting system over a conventional one was the benefit of reduced flood risk. For a passive tank of 100 m³, 66% of rainwater is stored in the tank and diverted to use rather than immediately into the stormwater drainage system. If the tank used smart RWH and collected more rainfall in peak times, the system would be much more effective. When the reduced flooding is considered, many other benefits are included in the analysis with no extra costs. Although infrequent, including savings on building, infrastructure damage and livestock damage would rapidly decrease metrics such as payback period, LC and BCR. If a small flood that would have caused as low as £10,000 of damage is prevented, rainwater harvesting becomes a very feasible option.

Furthermore, the reasons for an investigation into RWH are climate change, population growth and urbanisation. These will only increase water stress over time leading to more expensive and less reliable potable water. The savings made from the same amount of harvested rainwater will continue to increase and time goes on, whilst costs will only adjust for inflation (excluding unforeseen events). Therefore, the use of rainwater harvesting in the Filton development to assist conventional water supply in meeting non-potable demand and reduce stormwater stress on the local drainage system, is a feasible option.

4.3 Future Work

Whilst this report determines RWH is likely to be feasible for non-potable demand, there are many more potential avenues of investigation that can validate and improve the suggested system. One of these possibilities is the use of the system to meet non-potable demand of the YTL arena.

4.3.1 YTL Arena

The YTL Arena is the proposed development that will refurbish the Brabazon hangars into an entertainment complex. With a capacity of 17,080 people and expected to host over 1 million visitors a year, non-potable demand will come in large surges on evenings where events take place. For example, if 90% of those visitors needed to use the toilet and a toilet used 5 litres per flush, demand would reach 76m³. Using mains water only at the price used in this report (£1.2699 per m³), this would cost £96.50 per event. Assuming only four nights of events a week, that becomes £20,074 a year. A RWH system using the remaining two hangars as a catchment area could supply a proportion of this demand. However, due to the size and infrequent nature of the demand, large tank sizes would be required to reach a reasonable water saving efficiency. This may incur high capital costs which effects the feasibility of a system. To investigate whether RWH should be used, a similar report to this could be carried out. This could use the same historical data to create a better stochastic model, a different method to simulate demand and the same behavioural model.

4.3.2 Detailed Analysis on Stormwater Reduction

It has been explained that the rainwater harvesting system will bring many benefits by reducing the stormwater surges the drainage system will face in storm events. However, the details of the benefits are not specific. A comprehensive study into local past flooding events and predicted future patterns may determine if the Filton development is at risk from excess stormwater. It might be that even severe storms in the area can be managed safely by the existing sewage network. This would lessen the benefits of RWH as a stormwater storage system, leaving its sole purpose to reduce the strain on existing water demand. If this is the case, then there might be a possibility for large savings in reducing the size of the stormwater network. The local sewerage network (Wessex water) uses a combined sewer, transporting both sewage and surface run-off water. If the RWH system is significantly reducing the stormwater that discharges into the sewer, the capacity of the network can be smaller without any disadvantages. Although, it is possible that the area may be prone to flooding after development, which is why detailed analysis would be useful.

5 Conclusions

This purpose of this investigation was to determine the feasibility of a rainwater harvesting system as a complementary non-potable water supply and stormwater capture system at Filton development, Bristol. Although university data restrictions brought by the COVID-19 virus hindered many simulations and results, it is concluded that RWH is likely to be feasible.

The developed stochastic model for rainfall provided too many limitations to create accurate results. Periodicity and seasonal changes are very important patterns to consider in rainfall, with serious differences in optimum tank size when they are not included. Historical rainfall data from 2010, 2012 and 2018 proved reliable time series to test the RWH behavioural model, although the reduced time step from hourly to daily is likely to affect accuracy.

Using the Brabazon central hangar as a catchment area, the maximum water saving efficiency that could have been achieved for the year 2018 was 43.56%. The optimum tank size determined for a passive RWH system was 100 m³. Using a YBS model, this tank size gave a WS efficiency of 38.1%, SC efficiency of 87.5% and reliability of 28%. 100 m³ was chosen by comparing the costs of different tanks within a range to the yield savings they produced. Further analysis using levelized cost, benefit/cost ratio and payback period was intended before a conclusion on feasibility was reached. However, a similar RWH site at Exeter university which included operating and maintenance costs determined that their system was economically feasible.

Analysis on an active system instead of passive also could not be investigated effectively. Data could not be collected on the combined sewer for calculating total excess stormwater and further simulations on the set-point threshold could not be run. However, it was noted that implementing a set-point on the 100 m³ tank was not too detrimental on the WS efficiency, SC efficiency and reliability. They each dropped by only 2.56%, 4.79% and 0.82% respectively for a set-point 60% of the total volume. Therefore, if the total excess stormwater reduced by active RWH is significant enough, the active approach is more effective than the passive.

It is suggested that future work be carried out on the stormwater analysis to give a better understanding on how the local drainage network will benefit from stormwater reduction. There is also potential for another rainwater system (or increase on the proposed one) to meet the non-potable demand of the future YTL arena. Using the remaining hangars as a catchment area, a large amount of water demand could be saved. Finally, an investigation into a semi-centralised model is also recommended. By using multiple large volume tanks and adding

house roofs to the catchment area, there is a chance for the performance of the RWH system to be improved. It would give higher flexibility as each tank could be a different volume, and which tank each roof is allocated to can be optimised.

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Appendix A

As the project involved simulations and online data collection only, there was no laboratory or hazardous work. The only health and safety considerations taken were involved with posture, preventing eye strain and other computer related illnesses. Breaks were taken at regular intervals and seating with strong lumbar support was used.